

Quantum Free $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and Why Momentum Alone is Not Sufficient

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In physics (including classical physics), conservation of momentum is always considered, but one must be more careful with conservation of energy as it may include forms like sound etc. As a result, there is a tendency to focus on conservation of momentum all of the time, and conservation of particle energy only in elastic collisions. In addition to this, one may think of a particle striking a target, in which case two equal momentum (but different energies due to different v speed and m_0 rest mass) cause the same impact. In the case of an interaction with a potential, however, it is strictly energy considerations which are important classically, i.e. one uses $p \cdot p / 2m + V(x) = E$. Knowing momentum without rest mass is not sufficient. One may consider it unusual that one may consider two different scenarios, one which focuses only on momentum (impulse) or conservation of momentum in collisions while only energy is the focus in classical bound states or motion in $V(x)$.

Given the classical focus on momentum, imagine that one wishes to describe all free particles with different momenta as a uniform probability distribution such that a product of two probabilities for p_1, p_2 is the same as for p_3, p_4 if $p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$. (We use 1-dimension for simplicity.). One cannot use $P = 1/n$ because p is absent and $n \rightarrow \infty$. In one sense, all particles must have the same probability, but at the same time must contain extra information related to p for the conservation of p part of the problem.

The notion of a uniform distribution is independent of conservation of momentum, hence of p momentum. Conservation of momentum requires an explicit presence of p . As a result, there seems to be a paradox. One may, however, resolve this paradox by arguing that a probability is a mathematical way of presenting a subset of the information present. If one argues for a uniform probability, then it does not need to contain p , and one would have 1 as an unnormalized probability for any free particle p .

A different probability (representing a different subset of information) which respects all free particles as having the same weight, but includes p can also be constructed, namely $\exp(i C p)$. C is a constant introduced for unit issues. In this case, the modulus gives all free particle probabilities with p the same weight, but the presence of p allows one to have conservation of momentum. Given that momentum is the key variable that is conserved in classical physics, one should be satisfied with $\exp(i C p)$. One might argue that there is no need to consider energy E . We note, however, that if one has p, E_1 and $-p, E_2$ in a frame, then in a frame moving with $-v$, one has $gp + gvE_1 = p_1'$ and $p_2' = -gp + gvE_2$. Adding yields $gv(E_1 + E_2)$ and so energy automatically appears and cannot be discarded. Furthermore for p, E_1 and $-p, E_2$, $\exp(i C 0)$ is $\exp(i C gv(E_1 + E_2))$ as seen in the moving frame and so one is forced to consider conservation of energy together with momentum and include both p and E in the more detailed probability.

In other words, special relativity automatically links p and E in a 4-vector, leading to the idea that both are important. We argue that one cannot simply consider $\exp(i C p)$ due to special relativity. Both E and p must be considered together and this is a key idea, we argue, because if one wishes to have a Lorentz invariant probability, it must be in E and p , i.e. $-Et + px$. Instead of having a probability for an interaction with p given by $\exp(i C p)$, one has $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and we argue that this must have the same value in all frames for a particular interaction. One may note

that E and p are, on the one hand, separated allowing for impulse hit versus E related interactions, but that overall the probability for interaction includes both and it is the full $-Et+ipx$ which must be invariant. This further suggests that if one does not artificially force an interaction to occur at the center-of-mass, then x,t and $x+h\bar{p}/p, t+h\bar{E}/E$ are equally good points for the interaction. We argue that there is no need to force $x=vt$ because $\exp(-iEt+ipx) * \exp(iEt+ipx)$ already shows that one has uniformity, not only for any p,E , but also for any x, t , as there are now four variables. Thus, there is no reason to enforce $x=vt$ in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, when considering an interaction, we argue.

This means that one has two possible interactions at different x,t values, i.e. x,t and $x+h\bar{p}/p, t+h\bar{E}/E$. If one is unable to follow the interaction in time, but may follow it in space as in the case of 2-slits about $h\bar{p}/p$ apart or for a potential $V(x)$, then one may use the $\exp(ipx)$ part of the interaction probability piece by itself.

Thus, we argue that special relativity does not allow one to treat p independently of E . For example, for p values that are the same in one frame, but have E_1, E_2 , will be different in another frame. One must consider E and p together and so instead of creating a probability for p alone, one must create one for E,p and then impose Lorentz invariance which leads to different x,t pairs yielding the same probability value for an interaction, i.e. free particle quantum mechanics.

Classical Mechanics and Momentum Conservation Alone

Classical mechanics teaches one to always consider conservation of momentum in a calculation, but not conservation of energy, because although overall energy is conserved, there may be pieces of energy, due to sound etc, which cannot be easily calculated. Only in an elastic collision does one consider the conservation of kinetic energy. In the case of an interaction with a potential $V(x)$ (conservative potential), overall kinetic energy plus potential energy is conserved. Furthermore, if one has two identical momenta, but with different energies (i.e. different rest masses and v), then they will create the same impulse and one does not have to consider energy. This leads one to the notion that one may try to create a probability for a free particle which respects conservation of momentum alone.

Such a probability should be uniform for any free particle, but this means that one has $1/n$ where $n \rightarrow$ infinite. Nevertheless, the unnormalized probability is 1 for any free particle, but 1 does not contain any information about p and so cannot possibly be linked to conservation of momentum. One requires a second probability which contains p , but gives each $P_1(p)$ the sense of having the same weight. One may ask: How is it possible to have two probabilities? We argue that probability is a mathematical function for describing a subset of the full information in a problem. One may create one probability representing one subset and a second, representing a subset of this subset. The only requirement is that the two probabilities be consistent with each other. If 1 means that all p free particles have the same weight, a function containing p , which is clearly not 1, must have some feature which is the same for all particles and demonstrates this uniformity. We argue that one may create the probability:

$\exp(i C p)$ where C is constant for units and for simplicity, we focus on 1-dimension ((1))

This probability only depends on momentum and

$$\exp(i C p_1) \exp(i C p_2) = \exp(i C p_3) \exp(i C p_4) \text{ iff } p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4 \quad ((2))$$

As we have pointed out in different notes, one may have a p , E_1 and a p , E_2 in one frame. ((2)) only requires p and so both are good. The problem is that in another frame one p becomes $g p + g v E_1$ and the other, $g p + g v E_2$, where $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. They are not the same and so ((2)) would differ, which is a contradiction.

Here, we argue that the central idea is that because of special relativity, one must consider both E and p together. Even though classical physics focuses on p and conservation of momentum alone, in a frame moving with $-v$, one sees a mix of E and p

$$p' = g p + g v E \quad \text{where } g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((3))$$

As a result, what is p in one frame becomes a mixture of p and E in a second frame. In terms of conservation:

Consider p , E_1 and $-p$, E_2 , then

$$P_1' = g p + g v E_1 \quad \text{and } p_2' = -g p + g v E_2 \quad \text{so } p_1'+p_2' = g v (E_1+E_2) \quad ((4))$$

If one had, p_1 , E_3 , $-p_1$, E_4 in one frame, then this becomes E_3+E_4 , meaning that for conservation of momentum to hold in the second frame:

$$E_1+E_2 = E_3+E_4 \quad ((5))$$

In general, p_1 , E_3 and $-p_1$, E_4 does not give rise to $E_1+E_2 = E_3+E_4$. This means that one cannot simply consider $\exp(i C p)$. One must consider momentum and energy conservation together in a single frame.

This means that one must consider both E and p in a probability function and both p and E conservation in every frame. One cannot consider momentum alone, as one would think based only on momentum conservation. This means that one must generalize the probability to:

$$\exp(i C p + i C_1 E) \quad (\text{one dimension}) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } \exp(i C (g p + g v E) + i C_1 (g v p + g E)) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) in general is a different probability from ((6)) and this makes no sense because $\exp(i \text{ phase})$ is the probability value which should be frame invariant. This seems to force one to adopt a Lorentz invariant which includes both E and p . As a result, the key idea that both E and p must appear in the probability lead to:

$$\text{Probability} = \exp(-i E t + i p x) \quad ((8))$$

As a result, instead of the single variable p (one dimension), one has four variables. A free particle's center-of-mass follows $x=vt$, but ((8)) is both an interaction and position type of probability. It only becomes a position probability when one performs

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) * \exp(iEt+ipx) = 1 \quad ((9))$$

This means, we argue, that one does not have to enforce $x=vt$ on x,t in ((8)) as the modulus already indicates that one has uniform weight in space and that dt is the same in each dx . As a result, x,t may vary from $x=vt$ in ((8)). We note that the phase is key for a probability state and that given x,t , the same phase appears for:

$$x+h\bar{p}/p, \quad t+h\bar{h}/E \quad ((10))$$

((8)) was introduced in the first place to ensure momentum conservation, i.e. describe an interaction. As a result, an interaction linked to a fixed E,p may take place with the same probability at x,t and ((10)) suggesting that the interaction does not take place at $x=vt$. This means that given a two slit system, with slits separated about $h\bar{p}/p$, one may have probabilistic interaction with both slits according to the probability ((8)). As a probability, one would consider an OR situation. Given that one does not follow t in such an interaction, one may focus entirely on:

$$\exp(ipx) \text{ and } dx = h\bar{h}/p \quad ((11))$$

Then:

$$\text{Probability } 1 = \exp(i p \cdot r1) + \exp(i p \cdot r2) \quad ((12))$$

In order to find the spatial probability, one must use the rule ((9)) which converts from the $P1$ probability to the P classical spatial probability. This leads to:

$$\text{Classical spatial probability} = \{ \exp(i p \cdot r1) + \exp(i p \cdot r2) \} * \{ \exp(-i p \cdot r1) + \exp(-i p \cdot r2) \} \quad ((13))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical mechanics focuses on conservation of momentum, as kinetic energy is only conserved in elastic collisions. If one desires a probability which enforces conservation of momentum, one would first argue that any free particle has the same weight, i.e. that there is a uniform distribution. In such a case, the unnormalized probability is 1, but there is no information about momentum. Probability is a math construct which presents only a subset of the information available. The fact that p is not present in 1 is not a problem if one only wishes to deal with the notion of all free particles having the same weight. If one wishes to include p , in order to enforce conservation of momentum, one requires a second probability

function which does not violate the equal weight idea. We suggest that such a function is $\exp(i C p)$ (one dimension), with C accounting for units. The problem with this function is that even though it only considers p in one dimension and enforces conservation of momentum using product probabilities, if one has $p, E1$ and $-p, E2$ in one frame, then $\exp(i p C) \exp(-ip C)$ in the second frame would be $\exp(i C \gamma v(E1+E2))$. For another $p1, E3, -p1, E4$ one would have $\exp(i C \gamma v(E3+E4))$. This implies that one cannot only consider p conservation, but must also take into consideration E conservation in every frame. One must consider E and p together because of special relativity. Furthermore, given a probability with E, p , $\exp(i \text{ phase})$ describes the probability for a specific type of interaction as E and p describe the particle. This phase should not change from one frame to another as the probability for a certain interaction does not change even if E, p change as seen from a frame moving with constant $-v$. This suggests that one use a Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

At first one might insist one using $x=vt$ in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but the classical probability is given by $\exp(-iEt+ipx) \cdot \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and this not only gives a 1 for each free particle, but may also be interpreted as giving a 1 for each for each point in time and space. As a result, one is not restricted to x, t in $x=vt$ in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. X, t represent interaction t, x values and a unique phase describes a specific interaction for a fixed E, p . This means that x, t and $x+h\bar{v}/p, t+h\bar{v}/E$ represent the same unique phase and both may occur for the E, p interaction. As a result, given a 2-slit system, with slits about $h\bar{v}/p$ apart, one should have two probabilities which add in an OR situation, one for each slit, i.e. $\exp(ip \cdot r1) + \exp(ip \cdot r2)$, where $r1$, and $r2$ are vectors from the center of each slit to a point on the screen. To find the classical probability in space one may multiply the complex conjugate of this sum by the sum itself. This way, one arrives at a probability which loses the extra information of E, p , but retains x .